

Wire-speed DDoS Attack Mitigation using Hardware Acceleration of Programmable DPUs

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Abstract—Service providers face significant challenges from Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks since existing mitigation techniques, including various Machine Learning and flow-based approaches, often lack efficiency due to high latency and inadequate filtering. This paper proposes a novel DDoS mitigation strategy using programmable Data Processing Units (DPUs) to offload detection and mitigation processes, utilizing hardware acceleration. Our approach leverages DPUs to execute flow-based filtering, focusing on mitigating TCP SYN flood attacks. We demonstrate that our DPU-based hardware-accelerated framework successfully eliminates, after a fast learning phase, all the malicious traffic while maintaining high data throughput up to 100 Gbps.

Index Terms—DDoS, Data Processing Unit (DPU), Network Interface Card (NIC), smart NICs, BlueField, DOCA, Hardware acceleration

I. INTRODUCTION

Among the challenges posed by recent cybersecurity trends, Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks remain a major threat due to their potential to disrupt the legitimate use of services drastically [1]. DoS attacks become even more effective when executed as Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks, where distributed machines or sophisticated botnets, e.g., Mirai [2], can engage hundreds of thousands of devices globally to disrupt services.

A common technique employed in DDoS attacks is the TCP SYN flood attack. In this strategy, attackers flood a target server with TCP SYN (synchronize) packets, to which the server replies by allocating resources and sending back SYN-ACK (synchronize-acknowledgment) packets. However, the completion of these connections is prevented as the attackers do not return the necessary ACK packets, leading to an exhaustion of the server's TCP sessions table. This exhaustion prevents the server from handling legitimate requests, effectively denying service to authorized users [1].

Many techniques have been proposed to detect DDoS attacks, including rule-based, signature-based, commercial-based, Machine Learning (ML), anomaly-based, and flow-

based policies [3]–[6]. However, these methods typically introduce additional latency in detecting and mitigating attacks, which can be particularly problematic during high rates of attack activity, as a significant portion of the attack may not be handled promptly.

A promising solution to address TCP SYN flood attacks consists of offloading part or the entire detection and mitigation processes inside the Smart Network Interface Card (SmartNIC), saving all or part of the host resources. Unlike standard Network Interface Cards (NICs), SmartNICs feature a programmable System-on-Chip (SoC) multi-core CPU and run an operating system that facilitates extensive programmability. This allows for the hardware offloading of complex operations such as packet filtering, encryption, and regular expression matching. Notably, NVIDIA's BlueField SmartNICs, also known as Data Processing Units (DPUs), come equipped with the Data Center-on-a-Chip Architecture (DOCA) [7] as a software development kit (SDK) that enables the deployment and execution of custom programs. Among the DOCA available tools, the DOCA Flow module allows developers to build generic packet processing pipelines in hardware, thereby enhancing packet processing efficiency while saving limited CPU resources.

In this paper, we propose a DOCA Flow-based DDoS mitigation technique that is fully offloaded to the DPU, exploiting its programmability and hardware acceleration capabilities. Specifically, the application logic is implemented on the DPU's ARM processors, which delegate as many tasks as possible to the underlying hardware. This architecture ensures that the host system remains completely unaware of the security processes, allowing it to dedicate all its resources to handling business-critical workloads and applications. This advantage makes the proposed approach a suitable, cost-effective solution since the initial investment in a DPU to replace standard NICs and the software development costs are offset by significant savings in resource allocation and operational efficiency. In addition, the only architectural change required in existing systems is to replace the NIC plugged into the server with a DPU.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II discusses related works. Section III offers an architectural overview of the system; Section IV provides implementation details of the proposed schema; Section V shows system

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results and performance. Finally, Section VI concludes this work.

II. RELATED WORKS

Recently, considerable effort has been put into attempting to offload cyber-security operations inside SmartNICs. Wu et al. [8] proposed an on-device sequential learning semi-supervised anomaly detector-based intrusion detection system (ONLAD-IDS). They fully offloaded their IDS inside the DPU, running their application entirely on its ARM processors without exploiting any available hardware acceleration. This approach, while saving host CPU resources, does not fully benefit from the hardware acceleration capability offered by the DPU. Miano et al. [9] proposed a diverse range of applications (i.e., flow metering, port scan detection, and SYN flood attack detection) leveraging SmartNICs as high-performance accelerators for stream processing operations. They showed that their solution was able to analyze up to 40% more traffic compared to a pure software approach. Dimolianis et al. [10] proposed an IP-agnostic signature-based traffic classification and mitigation for DDoS attacks, developing eXpress Data Path (XDP) middleboxes operating as programmable Deep Packet Inspectors. However, relying on the Control Plane to reduce the number of extracted features and perform classification introduces some latency and consumes resources from external control systems.

Miano et al. [11] proposed a hybrid approach based on hardware and XDP/eBPF (extended Berkeley Packet Filter) offload strategy to assign a portion of DDoS mitigation rules to the SmartNIC. They evaluated the performance of the system while changing the load assigned by the host to the SmartNIC in the mitigation process. They achieved remarkable results in terms of reducing host CPU utilization while offloading totally or partially the mitigation procedure on the SmartNIC. They also highlighted performance degradation when relying on SmartNIC CPU resources once saturated all possible hardware-offloaded filtering rules, being able to effectively handle only approximately 1k attackers before having to involve the host. This limitation makes their solution unsuitable for large networks.

Despite these advancements, it is worth noticing that none of the aforementioned approaches is suitable for effectively blocking large-scale DDoS attacks solely using DPU resources within a few hundred milliseconds and at wire-speed.

III. ENABLING TECHNOLOGY: DPU ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 depicts the DPU building blocks and the way they are interconnected to intercept ingress traffic from both network and host, process it, and forward it to the egress port. Packets enter the DPU from either *P0* (Physical Port connected to the network) or *pf0hpf* (Physical Function connected to the host), two network interfaces for the uplink and for the host side, respectively. These ports can be bound to hardware-offloaded Open-Virtual-Switch (OVS) bridges by leveraging either Traffic Control (TC) or Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK)-optimized solutions to avoid pure software switch

bottlenecks. The goal of these bridges is to connect *P0* and *pf0hpf* to DPU-internal Scalable Functions, SF1 and SF2, respectively. The SFs consist of lightweight functions having a parent PCIe function on which they are deployed. They are able to access its capabilities and resources, as well as their dedicated queues (i.e., txq, rxq). Moreover, SFs enable multiple services to run concurrently on the DPU. At this stage, packets enter the programmable hardware pipes defined via DOCA Flow APIs. These pipes define the fate of the packets, being able to drop and modify them, send them to the CPU, or steer them directly to the other SF, bypassing the CPU itself. The application residing on top of the CPU, in our case, the DDoS mitigation one, is directly bound to SF1 and SF2. In this way, whenever a packet needs to be processed by the application, a hardware pipe, built in the environment initialization phase, can redirect it to the SFs queues. A Receive Side Scaling (RSS) [12] mechanism is used to load-balance the incoming traffic among the queues. Finally, in order to access and process those packets according to their needs, the application leverages DPDK APIs to retrieve them in polling mode from the queues, parse, and eventually forward them. Assigning one ARM core to a single tx-rx queues pair is recommended to avoid race conditions or performance degradation. Thanks to the DOCA Flow APIs, the application not only builds hardware pipes when setting up the environment but also orchestrates them at runtime by adding and removing entries as per its needs. Hardware pipes are able to match standard packet fields such as match IP source and destination address, L4 protocol, and L4 ports but also to forward or drop it according to the matched entry. They can also impress a per-entry defined metadata value on the packet, which can later be accessed by both subsequent pipes and ARMs.

Fig. 1. Data Processing Unit (DPU) Architecture

IV. PROPOSED DOCA FLOW-BASED DDoS MITIGATION SYSTEM

The key idea behind our solution relies on the ability to efficiently leverage the DPU programmability and hardware

offload capabilities at the same time. The DOCA Flow library has been exploited to define a set of hardware pipes in which as many traffic processing operations as possible have been offloaded. Each pipe, defined by calling native C APIs of the library, consists of match criteria, monitoring, and a set of actions. These building blocks have been used to monitor each source by updating per-flow counters, forwarding legitimate packets, dropping blacklisted source IP addresses, and writing per-flow metadata values. However, considering the stateless nature of hardware pipes, a stateful control logic is needed to dynamically orchestrate and update the pipes. This logic is deployed on the ARM cores and written in C programming language, including all the available C libraries to properly fill, update, query, and finally remove entries in the pipes. This distribution of tasks between the main two components of our system, namely the ARM cores and the offloading hardware, is explicitly highlighted in Figure 2.

A. Pipes Workflow

Once a packet enters the physical port P0 of the DPU, it reaches SF1 and enters into the *root pipe*, as depicted in Figure 2. This *root pipe* allows only IPv4 traffic to be forwarded to the next pipe of the proposed DOCA Flow-based DDoS mitigation system (IPv6 traffic is not addressed in this work). The *blacklist pipe* drops all the packets sent by blacklisted sources while forwarding the remaining to the *control pipe*. This *control pipe* is designed to hierarchically match among the pipe entries and forward packets to different destinations among *SYN pipe*, *TCP_COUNT pipe*, and *SF2*. *Control pipe* forwards the packet to *SF2* whenever the packet L4 protocol is different from TCP to directly reach the host. Conversely, if the packet L4 protocol is TCP, the SYN flag is active, and the number of SYN packets does not exceed a threshold imposed by the rate limiter, the packet is forwarded to the *SYN pipe*. If the packet L4 protocol is TCP but the SYN flag is not active, it is forwarded toward the *TCP_COUNT pipe*. While traversing the latter, if an entry matching the packet's source IPv4 address already exists, the byte and packet counters of this entry are updated, and the packet is forwarded to the host. Otherwise, it will be dropped. In the *SYN pipe*, if an entry matching the packet's source IPv4 address is present, a per-entry defined metadata value is impressed on the packet before redirecting it to the ARM cores according to an IP-based RSS mechanism. This metadata value is accessed by the ARMs on which our application is running, performing the tasks described in Algorithm 1. This metadata value consists of a specific value assigned by the ARMs to each source IPv4 address and pointing to the memory location where related IP information is stored (number of SYN packets, entry ID for *SYN pipe*, *TCP_COUNT pipe*, and *BLACKLIST pipe*). Only if a miss occurs in the *SYN pipe*, the packet will land in the *SYN_miss pipe*, where the metadata field is filled with a value equal to zero (i.e., regardless of its source IPv4 address) before redirecting the packet to the ARM cores as described for the *SYN pipe*. *SYN and SYN_MISS pipes*, since able to impress metadata information to the packet, which is accessible by the

application, can be seen as the connection point between the ARM cores and the offloading hardware. It is worth noting that thanks to the rate limiter bound to the entry for the SYN packets in the *Control pipe*, the maximum number of packets per second to be processed by the CPU is kept fixed. In this way, the resource-limited CPU is not overloaded during severe attacks, and the maximum number of SYN packets per second that will reach the host is kept controlled so that it will not crash. Regarding outgoing traffic, i.e., all the traffic sent by the host to the network is simply forwarded by a hardware pipe from *SF2* to *SF1*.

B. Application Logic

The multi-thread application running on top of the eight ARM cores plays a key role in making the system self-sustainable and flexible. The simplified pseudo-code of the application logic is detailed in Algorithm 1. Before starting

Algorithm 1 Application Logic pseudo-code

```

1: while true do
2:   poll RX queue for RX_packets
3:   if #RX_packets  $\neq$  0 then
4:     for packet in RX_packets do
5:       parse the packet
6:       if meta = 0 then
7:         start IP monitoring
8:         add packet to TX_packets
9:       else
10:        retrieve IP record from meta
11:        increase IP sent #SYN
12:        query #PKTs HW counter
13:        if #SYN/#PKTs  $\geq$  TH then
14:          blacklist the IP
15:          drop the packet
16:        else
17:          add packet to TX_packets
18:        end if
19:      end if
20:    end for
21:    send TX_packets to TX_queue
22:  end if
23:  manage entry aging
24: end while

```

the packet processing threads, DOCA Flow hardware pipes are instantiated. Then, each thread assigned to each ARM core starts to repeatedly probe in polling mode the assigned RX queue by using DPDK libraries. It is worth noting that only packets sent by *SYN and SYN_MISS pipes* end up in these queues, i.e., only those that need to be inspected deeply to detect the SYN flood attack. When packets arrive, these are parsed to access metadata and source IP address fields. Depending on the packet metadata value, if it is equal to zero or not, the thread immediately understands from which pipe it came. Thanks to this mechanism, the application understands whether the sender IP is either already under monitoring or

at different rates, with different numbers of malicious IPs, and to evaluate system performance.

B. Performance Evaluating

To evaluate DDoS Flow-based mitigation system's performance under normal conditions, and therefore not under attack, wire-speed TCP stateless traffic (i.e. not including TCP session establishment and termination) of different packet sizes has been generated, emulating legitimate traffic. Figure 4 shows the system behaviour when 64-byte and 1518-byte packet sizes have been set for legitimate traffic. For 64-byte packet size, our DDoS Flow-based mitigation system achieved up to 22 Gbps due to the smaller packet size. Once the packet size has been increased to 1518 bytes, the maximum achievable throughput of our system reached up to 100 Gbps, i.e., line-rate. This result has been included to show that our system did not affect the throughput, being able to achieve the maximum performance offered by the card itself for both packet sizes.

Starting from the experiment reported in Figure 4, malicious traffic has been added. We noticed that the attacks, regardless of their severity and scale, had almost no impact on legitimate traffic since already offloaded in hardware.

To generate the SYN flood DDoS traffic, 100-second attacks have been launched, relying on TRex. The SYN flood DDoS traffic consists of 64-byte packets sent at different rates with source IP addresses uniformly picked from a pool of addresses of different dimensions, emulating attacks of different severity and scale. Our system has been tested while under attack of various cumulative rates, up to 10 Gbps, including up to 500k attackers, entering up to 500k entries per pipe at application start-up. IP spoofing, not taken into account in this version of our system, will be considered in future works.

Figures 5 and 6 show the mitigation capability of the system when cumulative attacks of 500 Kpps were launched by a pool of 50k and 500k attackers, respectively. As it can be seen, mitigation does not depend neither on the number of malicious sources participating in the attack nor on how aggressive the attack is: all the packets sent by a malicious IP, once blacklisted, will be dropped. However, since the first packet sent by an attacker is not sufficient to detect its malicious behaviour by our system at this stage, it will not be dropped and will reach the host. It explains why a portion of malicious traffic is able to reach the host, and this portion is proportional to the number of attackers, as Figure 5 and 6 depict. To overcome this limitation and prevent the host from crashing in case of an attack carried out by an extremely large botnet, a meter has been exploited to keep the number of SYNs under a certain threshold, as shown in Figures 6, 5. The meter has been fine-tuned to accept no more than 250k SYNs per second, preventing the overload of the ARM cores of the DPU and the host targeted by the attack. Results show that, in the first learning phase, only a small portion of attacks can bypass the protection system. This phase lasts around 500ms for 50k attackers (i.e., IPs) and 1500ms for the extremely high number

of 500k attackers. Then, once the attackers are detected, all attack traffic is successfully blocked.

Fig. 4. System Throughput Recorded in VIAVI Hardware Traffic Generator

Fig. 5. DDoS Traffic Filtering Performance: 50k Attackers, 500 kpps

Fig. 6. DDoS Traffic Filtering Performance: 500k Attackers, 500 kpps

Finally, Figure 7 shows the effect of the attack on the legitimate stateful traffic, i.e., HTTP traffic that relies on TCP and, therefore, requires the three-way handshake to be completed for each session. A pool of 20k attackers, a cumulative rate of

20 Mpps, and a duration of 100 seconds have been set for the attack. Figure 7 shows that during the learning phase (around 3 seconds), 62% of legitimate traffic is successfully delivered. After this learning phase, the system blocks in the hardware all the packets sent by the IPs involved in the attack. It is worth noting that the proposed solution ensures that the server never stops working, even for very high attack rates.

Fig. 7. System Reaction Captured using Wireshark

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A novel DDoS detection and mitigation system specifically designed to operate on a Data Processing Unit (DPU) is proposed and successfully validated. The system addresses TCP SYN flood attacks by leveraging DPU hardware acceleration through DOCA Flow libraries and DPU's embedded CPUs. Under non-attack conditions, results show that the proposed system does not introduce performance degradation, successfully operating at wire-speed (i.e., 100 Gbps throughput from the network interface to host server). In the case of DoS attacks (i.e., originated from a single IP), the attack is successfully blocked after only a few packets, with no impact on legitimate traffic already offloaded in hardware and with only temporary degradation on legitimate stateful traffic. In the case of DDoS attacks originated from thousands of IPs (up to 500k tested), results show that detection and mitigation are successfully performed within a few hundred milliseconds with only limited impact on legitimate traffic throughput. Future works include extensive characterization of system performance, evaluating the portability of the proposed solution on different hardware platforms, and a possible comparison between them and with other existing solutions.

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